

The Management of English Teaching at Foreign Language Centers in Hanoi in the Context of Integration

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ABSTRACT: This research focuses on analyzing the current situation of the management of English teaching at private foreign language centers in Hanoi. Research results show that the surveyed foreign language centers have performed to a fairly good level the management contents of English teaching at private foreign language centers in Hanoi in the context of integration. In particular, the foreign centers have performed quite well the contents of input management, process management, output management and management of contextual factors affecting English teaching at private foreign language centers in Ha Noi in the context of integration. However, there are still some issues that management subjects need to improve, such as the management of admissions, teacher training, and the collection of student feedbacks.

KEY WORDS: Management of English Teaching; Private Foreign Language Centers; The Context of Integration

1. INTRODUCTION

Globalization has been strongly promoting international and regional integration. Integration has become a big trend of the world, being the policy choice of most countries for development. In the context of integration and the fourth industrial revolution, along with the rapid development of science and technology, future generations of citizens need to be equipped with new capabilities and skills to be able to succeed in a globally competitive environment. In this regard, the Resolution No. 29-NQ/TW dated November 4, 2013 of the 11th Central Executive Committee of the Communist Party of Vietnam on the “fundamental and comprehensive renovation of education and training, meeting the requirements of industrialization and modernization in the conditions of socialist-oriented market economy and international integration” has determined the goal of: “Actively integrating into the world in education and training on the basis of maintaining independence and, sovereignty, ensuring the socialist orientation; preserving and promoting the nation's cultural values; selectively absorbing the cultural quintessence and scientific and technological achievements of mankind; perfecting bilateral and multilateral cooperation mechanisms; implementing international commitments on education and training”. [8]

English is a global language: it is the official language of nearly 60 countries and territories, and also the official language of the EU [7]. Therefore, this foreign language plays a very important role in the current globalization and integration era. In Vietnam, English is one of the compulsory and important conditions for students at all levels and in the process of studying at school, in order to help them have enough foreign language ability to use it independently and confidently in communicating, learning and working in an integrated, multilingual, multicultural environment. This will make foreign languages become the strength of the Vietnamese people, serving the cause of industrialization and modernization of the nation.

On January 23, 2019, Hanoi issued Plan No. 28 on teaching and learning foreign languages in high schools and centers for vocational education and continuing education in the city until 2025 [9] to improve the quality of English teaching and learning in Hanoi.

A host of new foreign language centers are opened every year, many of which are private foreign language centers. In addition to the language centers of poor quality, a few foreign language centers have affirmed themselves by being granted certificates of quality management systems from foreign units. Foreign language centers have helped learners access new languages quickly and effectively. The explosion of foreign language centers leads to increased competition. Therefore, ensuring the quality of teaching is a prerequisite related to the existence of these foreign language centers. This requires managers in foreign centers to have measures to help students develop good communication skills (listening, speaking, reading, writing), academic thinking (taking notes, summarizing, analyzing, synthesizing, ..) and develop teamwork skills, critical thinking as well as presentation skills. In addition,

technology is necessary in teaching with the support of new robots, software and applications to help improve the quality of English teaching and learning.

Therefore, this article will focus on analyzing and pointing out the current situation of the management of English teaching at private foreign language centers in Hanoi in the context of integration to have an accurate assessment of the situation, serving as a basis for proposing solutions to improve the effectiveness of English teaching at foreign centers in Hanoi to meet the requirements of integration.

2. STUDY AREA, RESEARCH SUBJECTS AND RESEARCH METHODS

2.1. Study area and research subjects

This study was conducted in English centers in 07 urban districts, 02 rural districts and 01 suburban town (a total of 20 English centers) of Hanoi, namely Ba Dinh; Hai Ba Trung; Hoang Mai; Thanh Xuan; Cau Giay; Bac Tu Liem; Nam Tu Liem; Son Tay; Chuong My; Dan Phuong.

The English centers surveyed in this research include 20 centers, of which 15 are in the inner city and 5 are in the suburbs, located in 10 districts of Hanoi city.

In terms of scale, there are 4 large-scale English centers (with a system of smaller centers), 11 medium-sized English centers and 5 small-scale English centers. Foreign language centers are usually located in the inner city where there is a large demand for learning English.

2.2. Research methods

The main method used in this study is the survey-by-questionnaire method. The data obtained from this method is processed by the statistical software SPSS 20.0.

3. Result and discussion

The current situation of the management of English teaching at private foreign language centers in Hanoi in the context of integration is analyzed through an assessment of the current situation of managing input factors, process factors, output factors and contextual factors affecting the English teaching at private foreign language centers. The research results are presented in detail below.

3.1. The current situation of managing input factors for English teaching at private foreign language centers in Hanoi in the context of integration

Table 1: The current situation of managing input factors for English teaching at private foreign language centers in Hanoi in the context of integration

No.	Content	Average score (AS)	Standard deviation (SD)
1	The management of admissions	4.01	0.67
2	The management of teachers	3.87	0.68
3	The management of teaching objectives	4.00	0.66
4	The management of teaching content and syllabi	4.06	0.71
5	The management of English teaching conditions	4.00	0.70
	Overall average score	3.98	0.68

The survey results are summarized in the above data table, with the overall average score of 3.98; and standard deviation of 0.68. This shows that the management of input factors for English teaching at private foreign language centers in Hanoi in the context of integration is performed at a good level. The results of this study have shown that the management subjects have performed to a good extent the management contents belonging to input management, including the management of admissions, the management of teachers, the management of teaching objectives, the management of teaching content and syllabi and the management of English teaching conditions

All aspects of input management for English teaching at private foreign language centers in Hanoi in the context of integration have reached a good level of performance, with the average score ranging from 3.87 to 4.06. As follows:

The management of admissions has the AS of 4.01; and SD of 0.67, reaching the good level of performance. This result has shown that these English centers perform well in admission planning, admission announcement and content preparation for student counseling. The determination of the entrance standards for each course and the organization of enrollment and counseling are fully informed and clear, and the supervision of admission activities and counseling is also done in accordance with the norms and regulations. The aspect "Regular self-assessment and proposal of measures to improve admissions at the english center" has a good average level, but compared to the aspects considered in this content, it has the lowest average score. Therefore, english centers should pay more attention to this aspect.

The management of teachers has an overall average score of 3.87; and standard deviation of 0.68, reaching the level of good performance. Thus, the management subjects at the surveyed English centers have performed to a good extent the following contents: Planning for admision; Evaluating and retraining teachers periodically and in accordance with the training needs; Developing criteria for evaluating teacher quality; Building an appropriate organizational structure with suitable powers and responsibilities to ensure the quality of the management and teaching; Supervising the recruitment, evaluation and training activities of teachers at the English centers. However, among the aspects considered in this management content, the aspect of "Directing the selection and invitation of experts to train teachers to improve teaching quality" and "Organizing training activities for teachers (including a reward and punishment mechanism for individuals performing this activity)" are assessed at the average score of 3.75 and 3.76, respectively, which is lowest of the 9 aspects considered under this management content. Therefore, the management subjects at the studied language centers need to have more appropriate and effective management measures in inviting experts to train teachers; and organizing teacher training activities.

The management of teaching objectives is assessed with the average score = 4.0; SD = 0.66, which is at the good level. This means that the survey subjects have a quite similar assessment that the management of teaching objectives in the context of integration is done at a good level. It can be said that the language centers have done quite well in planning for teachers to develop teaching objectives suitable for each lesson and each course. The formulation and implementation of teaching objectives appropriate to each lesson and each course (criteria 3) and the supervision of developing and implementing suitable teaching objectives for each lesson and each course (criteria 4) are also rated at good level and they rank 2nd and 3rd in the assessment of administrators and teachers. However, criteria such as "Developing criteria for assessing teaching objectives suitable to the context of integration " and "Regularly assessing the suitability of teaching objectives by considering the results achieved after each lesson and each course to take appropriate measures to improve teaching quality to meet the current context of integration" have the lowest average score among the 5 criteria under this management content. Therefore, language centers should strengthen the development of criteria for evaluating teaching objectives in the direction of ensuring quality as well as regularly assesss the relevance of teaching objectives with the results achieved after each lesson and each course to take appropriate measures to improve teaching quality. The two criteria are closely related to each other. When the evaluation criteria are clear and concise, the evaluation will be more effective, thereby offering effective measures to help improve the quality of the management of teaching objectives.

The management of teaching content and syllabi has an overall AS of 4.06 and SD of 0.71, which is at the good level. This means that the survey subjects assess that the management of teaching content and syllabi in the context of integration has been done at a fairly good level.

The management of teaching conditions has an overall average score of 4.00 and standard deviation of 0.70. This means that the survey subjects assess that the management of facilities at the english centers in the context of integration has been done at a good level. The management subjects at the studied foreign language centers have performed quite well in planning for construction, procurement, use, maintenance, and upgrading of facilities at the centers as well as the construction of criteria to evaluate the use of facilities at the english centers. Besides, criteria of researching and investing in facilities and equipment to improve teaching quality; Monitoring the construction, procurement, use, maintenance and upgrade of facilities at these centers and evaluate the efficiency of the use of facilities from which to propose measures to upgrade and maintain have also been done quite effectively. However, criteria such as "Organizing the construction, procurement, use, maintenance and upgrade of facilities at the center" and "Organize the training of personnel to perform the management and make most use of facilities and equipment for teaching" have the lowest average score compared to 7 criteria considered in this management content. Therefore, english centers should pay more attention to organizing the construction, procurement, use, maintenance and upgrading of facilities at the center and organize training of personnel to perform management tasks. and make the best use of facilities and equipment for teaching.

3.2. The current situation of managing process factors for English teaching at private foreign language centers in Hanoi in the context of integration

Table 2: The current situation of managing process factors for English teaching at private foreign language centers in Hanoi in the context of integration

No.	Content	Average score (AS)	Standard deviation (SD)
1	Managing the teaching activities of teachers	3.98	0.71
2	Managing the learning activities of students	3.96	0.67
3	Managing exams, tests, and the assessment of English learning results	4.02	0.69
	Overall average score	3.99	0.69

The survey results are summarized in the above data table, with the overall average score of 3.99 and standard deviation of 0.68. This shows that the management of elements in the English teaching process at foreign language centers in Hanoi in the context of integration has been done at a good level. The results of this study have shown that the management subjects have performed to a good extent the management content belonging to process management, including managing the English teaching activities of teachers, managing the learning activities of students, and managing exams, tests, and the assessment of English learning results.

Among the aspects of this management content, the aspect "Managing exams, tests, and the assessment of English learning results" has the highest average score compared to the three aspects considered under this management content, with AS = 4.02; SD = 0.69. In fact, English centers have planned to develop methods and forms of assessing students' learning. They have also developed assessment criteria and assessment processes; organized the construction of a bank of exam questions; organized and supervised the development and assessment of students' learning outcomes.

The aspect of "Teacher's English teaching management" has the second highest average score, at 3.98; and SD = 0.71, which is at the good level. The centers have quite well managed the teacher's lesson preparation, the teacher's classroom activities, and the teacher's implementation of teaching methods.

Finally, the aspect of "Managing the learning activities of students" is assessed with the average score of 3.96; SD = 0.67. English centers have done well in advising on setting teaching objectives and making learning plans for students, which motivates students to ensure the set goals and monitor and track the progress of learners (continuing, stopping, dropping out, pass/dropout rate). However, through research results as well as in-depth interviews with administrators and teachers, it also shows that centers do not pay much attention to helping students form learning methods, nor creating favorable conditions for students to develop their abilities and promote their own learning. This is an important content that the management subjects at English centers need to focus on and take more appropriate and effective management measures.

3.3. The current situation of managing output factors for English teaching at private foreign language centers in Hanoi in the context of integration

Table 3: The current situation of managing output factors for English teaching at private foreign language centers in Hanoi in the context of integration

No.	Content	Average score (AS)	Standard deviation (SD)
1	Managing the assessment of outputs and the issue of certificates of course completion for students	4.04	0.70
2	Managing the collection of student feedbacks	3.83	0.68
	Overall average score	3.93	0.69

The survey results are summarized in the above data table, with the overall average score of 3.93; SD = 0.69. This shows that the output management of English teaching at foreign language centers in Hanoi in the context of integration has been done at a good level. The results of this study have shown that the management subjects have performed quite well the management contents belonging to the output management factors, including managing the assessment of outputs and the issue of certificates of course completion for students and managing the collection of student feedbacks. As follows:

Managing the assessment of outputs and the issue of certificates of course completion for students is assessed with an average score of 4.04. This means that the survey subjects have assessed the content of managing the assessment of outputs and the issue of certificates of course completion for students at a fairly good level. The management of implementing aspects of this management content includes planning the collection of feedbacks from students about teaching and learning activities at the center; Defining criteria for collecting student feedbacks; Organizing the collection of student feedbacks; Supervising the collection of student feedbacks; Evaluating student output (results of final exams, university exams, certification exams, communication ability, ability to use English at work,...); and from the evaluation, the measures to improve the quality of teaching and learning activities of the English centers are proposed. However, in this management content, there are 2 criteria with a lower average score than the remaining criteria, namely "Organizing the collection of student feedbacks" and "from the evaluation, the measures to improve the quality of teaching and learning activities of the English centers are proposed", with average score of 3.77. Therefore, these are the issues that the management subjects at the studied foreign language centers need to focus on in order to have better management results.

3.4. The current situation of managing contextual factors for English teaching at private foreign language centers in Hanoi in the context of integration

The extent that factors affect the management of English teaching at private foreign language centers in the context of integration according to management staff and teachers surveyed by the author is shown in the following data table.

Table 4. The extent that factors affect the management of English teaching at private foreign language centers in the context of integration

No.	Content	Management staff		Teachers	
		AS	SD	AS	SD
1	Roles and capacities of the team involved in the management of English centers.	4.28	0.61	4.01	0.81
2	Decentralization in the management of teaching at English centers	3.76	0.69	3.66	0.82
3	Qualifications, qualities and capabilities of English teachers	4.70	0.54	4.35	0.81
4	The environment inside English centers	4.04	0.64	4.19	0.83
5	The environment outside English centers	3.48	0.71	3.56	0.83
6	The advancement and application of science and technology	3.86	0.67	3.82	0.78
7	Guidelines, institutions and policies of the nation	3.84	0.79	3.78	0.85
	Overall average score	3.99	0.65	3.91	0.81

From Table 4, it shows that there is a consensus between management staff and teachers when assessing the qualifications, qualities and capabilities of English teachers, which have the greatest influence on the quality of English teaching at English centers. (at a very influential level). It is followed by the roles and capacities of the team involved in the management of English centers, and the environment inside English centers. The factors with less influence are: The advancement and application of science and technology; Guidelines, institutions and policies of the nation; Decentralization in the management of teaching at English centers and the environment outside English centers. This shows that according to the assessment of administrators and teachers, the factors inside the foreign language center have a greater influence on the quality of English teaching than the factors outside the foreign language centers.

4. CONCLUSION

The research results on the current situation of the management of English teaching at foreign language centers in Hanoi in the context of integration are analyzed through an assessment of the current situation of managing input factors, process factors, output factors and contextual factors affecting the English teaching at foreign language centers. Research results show that the surveyed foreign language centers have performed to a fairly good level the management of English teaching at private language centers in Hanoi in the context of integration. Specifically, foreign centers have performed quite well the contents of input management, process management, output management and management of contextual factors affecting English teaching at foreign language centers in Ha Noi in the context of integration.

The research results also show that the management subjects at the studied foreign language centers have focused and performed better on the management of the English teaching process at foreign language centers in the context of integration, which has managed quite well the teaching activities teachers, including the management of lesson preparation, implementation of classroom teaching activities, the use of English teaching methods.

The management subjects in the survey have also focused on and managed to well perform the input elements of English teaching at foreign language centers in Hanoi in the context of integration. The management subjects have performed to a good extent the management contents belonging to input management, including the management of admissions, the management of teachers, the management of teaching objectives, the management of teaching content and syllabi and the management of English teaching conditions. However, some aspects of this management content need to be paid more attention, such as Regular self-assessment; proposal of measures to improve admissions at the english center; and training English teachers.

The output management of English teaching at foreign language centers in Hanoi in the context of integration has not been done as well as input and process management. In particular, the management subjects need to focus and have better management measures in such aspects as "Organizing the collection of student feedbacks" and "from the evaluation, the measures to improve the quality of teaching and learning activities of the english centers are proposed".

There are many contextual factors that have an impact on the management of English teaching at foreign language centers in the context of integration. However, there are some factors that are more influential, which are the qualifications, qualities and capabilities of English teachers; the roles and capacities of the team involved in the management of English centers; and the environment inside the English centers. .

This research result is an important practical basis for the management subjects of English teaching at the foreign language centers in Hanoi to find more appropriate and effective management measures to better implement the management contents of English teaching at foreign language centers in the context of integration.

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